

pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1): Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

shriprakash sinha

Independent Researcher; Orcid : 0000-0001-7027-5788

104-Madhurisha Heights Phase 1, Risali, Bhilai-490006, India

Abstract

Background : PYCR1 catalyzes the NAD(P)H-dependent conversion of pyrroline-5-carboxylate to proline. It has been implicated in progeroid disease, Autosomal-recessive cutis laxa type 2, geroderma osteodysplasticum, mental retardation, non-small cell lung cancer, prostate cancer, Hutchinson-Gilford progeria syndrome, human malignant melanoma, hepatocellular carcinoma, bladder cancer, nasopharyngeal cancer, pancreatic cancer, esophageal squamous cell carcinoma, colon adenocarcinoma and glioma. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of PYCR1, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

^{*}ML dicoveries of PYCR1 synergy in Meningiomas

Email address: sinha.shriprakash@yandex.com (shriprakash sinha)

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Meningioma	2
1.1.1	World Health Organization (WHO) classification	2
1.1.2	Historical perspective	3
1.1.3	Pathophysiology	3
1.2	pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1)	4
1.3	Roles of PYCR1 in different disease	5
1.4	Insight behind the work	8
1.5	Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution	8
2	Methods	9
2.1	Static data from Patel et al. [1]	9
2.2	Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]	9
2.3	Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R	10
2.4	Regarding biological insight	10
3	Results & Discussion	11
3.1	PYCR1 related synergies	11
3.1.1	PYCR1 - individual genes	11
4	Conclusion	17

1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatic, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecortius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1)

Pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase (PYCR) catalyzes the final step in proline synthesis by NAD(P)H-dependent reduction of pyrroline-5-carboxylate. Merrill et al. [13] purified and characterized this enzyme from human erythrocytes. They observed that the purified enzyme showed kinetic characteristics similar to those previously described for whole red cell homogenates. The V_{max} was observed to be 10-fold higher and the K_m for pyrroline-5-carboxylate was 7-fold higher with NADH versus NADPH as cofactor. Further, the affinity for NADPH was found to be 15-fold higher than that for NADH. Erythrocyte PYCR was competitively inhibited by $NADP^+$. Thus, they suggested that, in some cell types including human erythrocytes, a physiologic function of PYCR is the generation of $NADP^+$.

PYCR (EC 1.5.1.2) catalyzes the NAD(P)H-dependent conversion of pyrroline-

5-carboxylate to proline. Dougherty et al. [14] cloned a human PYCR cDNA by complementation of proline auxotrophy in a *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* mutant strain, DT1100. They screened 10(5) transformants, using a HepG2 cDNA library in a yeast expression vector, two of which gained proline prototrophy. They observed that the plasmids in both contained similar 1.8-kilobase inserts, which when reintroduced into strain DT1100, conferred proline prototrophy.

1.3. Roles of PYCR1 in different disease

Autosomal-recessive cutis laxa type 2 (ARCL2) is a multisystem disorder characterized by the appearance of premature aging (progeroid appearance), wrinkled and lax skin, joint laxity, a general developmental delay and mental retardation. It includes a family of clinically overlapping conditions with confusing nomenclature, generally requiring molecular analyses for definitive diagnosis and 6 genes are currently known to mutate to yield one of these related conditions. Guernsey et al. [15] ascertained a cohort of typical ARCL2 patients from a subpopulation isolate within eastern Canada and found that the single nucleotide change led to a missense mutation adjacent to a splice junction in the gene encoding PYCR1. Their bioinformatic analysis predicted a pathogenic effect of the variant on splice donor site function. Thus their results supported a significant role for proline in normal development.

Homozygosity mapping in several kindreds with ARCL identified a candidate region on chromosome 17q25. Via high-throughput sequencing, Reversade et al. [16] found disease-causing mutations in the gene PYCR1 (involved in proline metabolism), localized to mitochondria. Knocking down of the orthologous genes in *Xenopus* and zebrafish, led to the observation of epidermal hypoplasia and blistering that was accompanied by a massive increase of apoptosis. Their findings linked mutations in PYCR1 to altered mitochondrial function and progeroid changes in connective tissues.

Geroderma osteodysplasticum is a rare autosomal recessive disorder characterized by wrinkled skin on the dorsum of the hands and feet, osteopenia, prognathism, and an elongated and lax face. The mutated gene was identified as GORAB (SCYL1BP1). As well, the PYCR1 gene also was shown to be mutated in a similar disease, designated cutis laxa, autosomal recessive, type IIB (ARCL2B) or cutis laxa with progeroid features. Yildirim et al. [17] described the clinical findings in four affected individuals in a family afflicted with **geroderma osteodysplasticum**, with **mental retardation** and a homozygous mutation in PYCR1. They observed that while the patients with GORAB mutations had severe osteopenia, the patients with PYCR1 mutations had severe mental retardation. They concluded that the phenotype caused by PYCR1 mutations corresponded to geroderma osteodysplasticum rather than ARCL2B.

Hong et al. [18] performed RNA-sequencing (RNA-seq) to investigate potential fusion genes and alternative splicing in **non-small cell lung cancer** and found ITGB4 and PYCR1 were top genes that showed significant tumor specific splice variants.

Zeng et al. [19] found that PYCR1 was highly expressed in **prostate cancer** (PCa) tissues and then knocked down PYCR1 in PCa cell lines (DU145, PC-3 and LNCap) via lentivirus-mediated gene delivery and analyzed its biological function. PYCR1 knockdown revealed downregulated expression levels of cell cycle regulatory proteins, including CDK1, CDK2, CDK4 and Cyclin B1 and cell apoptotic-related proteins,

including cleaved caspase 3 and cleaved PARP were increased in PCa cells. These results show the functions of PYCR1 in PCa tumorigenesis for the first time and suggest that PYCR1 might be a good potential therapy approach for treating PCa.

Juvenile segmental progeroid syndromes are characterized by signs of premature aging in childhood. **Hutchinson-Gilford progeria syndrome** (HGPS), caused by a recurrent de novo synonymous LMNA mutation resulting in aberrant splicing and generation of a mutant product called progerin, is a prototypical example of such disorders. Lessel et al. [20] performed a study aimed at explaining the underlying genetic cause of 14 previously undiagnosed, clinically heterogeneous, non-LMNA-associated juvenile progeroid patients. They expanded the clinical spectrum associated with PYCR1 mutations by showing that they can somewhat resemble HGPS in the first year of life.

Human **malignant melanoma** (MM) is a highly malignant tumor of cutaneous melanocytes and Ye et al. [21] investigated the cellular effects of PYCR1 in the MM - A375 and M14 cell lines. To gain more insight into the role of PYCR1 in tumor growth, they analyzed the AKT phosphorylation level in PYCR1-specific siRNA (siPYCR1) and negative control (NC) cells. Their biochemical analysis revealed an increase in PYCR1 expression in human MM samples while silencing of PYCR1 suppressed the proliferation and migration of A375 and M14 cells. The observed enhanced apoptosis in PYCR1 knockdown cells was consistent with an increased level of markers of apoptosis and siPYCR1 inhibited AKT phosphorylation, as well as the expression of its downstream protein, P70, thus pointing to the fact that PYCR1 promoted cell growth of the MM cell lines A375 and M14 through stimulation of the AKT pathway. Thus they concluded that PYCR1 promoted tumor progression through the AKT pathway in human MM in vitro.

Zhuang et al. [22] explored the mechanisms of PYCR1 on cell growth and survival in **hepatocellular carcinoma** (HCC). They found that PYCR1 levels were up-regulated in HCC tumor tissues than adjacent normal liver tissues. Further, the c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) signaling pathway significantly altered, and insulin receptor substrate 1 (IRS1) were significantly down-regulated by PYCR1 interference in both mRNA and protein levels. They concluded that PYCR1 interference could inhibit cell proliferation and promote cell apoptosis in HCC through regulating JNK/IRS1 pathway.

N6-methyladenosine is methylation of adenosine base at the 6th nitrogen position, which is the dominant methylation modification in both message and non-coding RNAs. Dysregulation of RNA m6A methylation causes tumorigenesis in humans. The key N6-methyladenosine demethylase fat-mass and obesity-associated protein (FTO) is negatively correlated with the overall survival of bladder cancer patients. Song et al. [23] demonstrated that the post-translational deubiquitination by USP18 up-regulated the protein but not mRNA of FTO in bladder cancer tissues and cells. Because of this, it was observed that FTO decreased N6-methyladenosine methylation level in PYCR1 and stabilized PYCR1 transcript to promote **bladder cancer** initiation and progression.

Molecular mechanism of the hsa-miR-150-5p+PYCR1 axis in nasopharyngeal cancer has remained unclear. To identify the mechanism of the hsa-miR-150-5p-PYCR1 axis, Li et al. [24] measured the expression of hsa-miR-150-5p and PYCR1 in **nasopharyngeal cancer** tissues and cells by RT-qPCR. They confirmed the interaction between hsa-miR-150-5p and PYCR1 and clarified that hsa-miR-150-5p attenuated nasopharyngeal carcinogenesis by reducing the PYCR1 expression levels. This pro-

vided a new perspective of nasopharyngeal cancer involving both hsa-miR-150-5p and PYCR1 for the treatment of nasopharyngeal cancer.

Wang et al. [25] studied the effect of PYCR1 on the growth of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) cells. They found higher expression of PYCR1 in **pancreatic cancer** tissues than in paired adjacent normal pancreatic tissue. Further, in vitro, it was observed that the downregulation of PYCR1 expression inhibited the cell proliferation and colony formation, and increased apoptosis in PANC-1 cells and AsPC-1 cells compared with the shCtrl group. And in vivo, PYCR1 interference also significantly inhibited tumor growth both in the tumor volume and weight.

Qian et al. [26] explored the role and mechanism of hsa_circ_0000705 (circ_0000705) in **esophageal squamous cell carcinoma** (ESCC). They found up-regulated circ_0000705 expression in ESCC tissues and cell lines, and high circ_0000705 expression was correlated with poor survival as it facilitated cell proliferation, invasion, migration and proline metabolism of ESCC cells. Further, they observed that the inhibitory effects of circ_0000705 knockdown on cell invasion, migration and proline metabolism were partly rescued by miR-621 inhibition or PYCR1 over-expression. Furthermore, circ_0000705 expression was negatively (positively) correlated with miR-621 (PYCR1) expression in ESCC tissues. They observed that, mechanistically, circ_0000705 acted as a ceRNA by sponging miR-621, thereby facilitating PYCR1 expression in ESCC cells. In conclusion, they showed that circ_0000705 promoted proline metabolism and malignant progression of ESCC via regulation of the miR-621/PYCR1 axis.

Zhou et al. [27] clarified the role of PYCR1 and its interaction with SLC25A10 in a chemotherapeutic agent 5-fluorouracil (5-FU)'s toxicity to colorectal cancer cells. They detected PYCR1 and SLC25A10 expressions in The Cancer Genome Atlas database and **colon adenocarcinoma** (COAD) clinical samples. Further, it was observed that PYCR1 overexpression inhibited lipid reactive oxygen species production and promoted SLC25A10 expression in colorectal cancer cells. In contrast, PYCR1 silencing enhanced the antitumor effects of 5-FU. Also, ferroptosis inhibitor deferoxamine suppressed the antitumor effects of PYCR1 silencing, while ferroptosis inducer erastin inhibited the protumor effects of PYCR1 overexpression. They also observed that SLC25A10 overexpression reversed the antitumor effects of PYCR1 silencing in vitro and inhibited the antitumor effects of erastin in vivo. Thus, PYCR1 promoted colorectal tumor growth and desensitized colorectal cancer cells to 5-FU cytotoxicity by preventing apoptosis and ferroptosis.

Zhang et al. [28] explored the expression of PYCR1 in glioma-associated cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs) and analyzed the effects of PYCR1 expression in CAFs on the proliferation of C6 **glioma**. They observed the co-occurrence of PYCR1 and COL1A1 upregulation in the rat glioma, and PYCR1 was expressed in CAFs. The CAF coculture enhanced the invasion and proliferation of C6 cells and the angiogenesis of MUEVCs. Moreover, they found the effects of CAF coculture were increased with PYCR1 expression in the CAF. When they silenced PYCR1, they found suppression of the migration and invasion of C6 cells, and decreased the levels of COL1A1 and VEGF-A proteins in C6 cells.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations

via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [29] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [30] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [30].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [31]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [32], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank}

Joachims [29] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [29]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [33], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine

ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. PYCR1 related synergies

Note - PYCR1 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of PYCR1 were recorded.

3.1.1. PYCR1 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with PYCR1 showed high rankings - semaphorin 3F (SEMA3F), CD38 molecule (CD38), CD4 molecule (CD4), arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase (ALOX5), CD74 molecule (CD74), RUNX family transcription factor 3 (RUNX3), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family A member 2 (APBA2), collagen type IX alpha 2 chain (COL9A2), collagen type XI alpha 1 chain (COL11A1), tetraspanin 32 (TSPAN32), glypican 4 (GPC4), integrin subunit beta 5 (ITGB5), matrix metalloproteinase 2 (MMP2), solute carrier family 23 member 2 (SLC23A2), solute carrier family 22 member 17 (SLC22A17), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 5 (PCSK5), DNA meiotic recombinase 1 (DMC1), nuclear factor of activated T cells 4 (NFATC4), CD40 molecule (CD40), regulating synaptic membrane exocytosis 4 (RIMS4), C-C motif chemokine ligand 22 (CCL22), platelet derived growth factor receptor like (PDGFRL), epoxide hydrolase 3 (EPHX3), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), endoglin (ENG), cholinergic receptor nicotinic epsilon subunit (CHRNE), contactin associated protein 1 (CNTNAP1), peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22), tripartite motif containing 2 (TRIM2), crystallin alpha B (CRYAB), tetraspanin 11 (TSPAN11), SAM and SH3 domain containing 1 (SASH1), vanin 1 (VNN1), growth hormone receptor (GHR), par-3 family cell polarity regulator beta (PARD3B), Wnt ligand secretion mediator (WLS), immunoglobulin superfamily member 21 (IGSF21), patched 2 (PTCH2), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 2 (ENPP2), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), PDZ and LIM domain 2 (PDLIM2), cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1 (CRISPLD1), C-C motif chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), basic helix-loop-helix family member e41 (BHLHE41), hematopoietic cell signal transducer (HCST), transmembrane protein 35A (TMEM35A),

sarcoglycan epsilon (SGCE), palladin, cytoskeletal associated protein (PALLD), FCH and mu domain containing endocytic adaptor 1 (FCHO1), leukocyte immunoglobulin like receptor B2 (LILRB2), microtubule associated protein 1B (MAP1B), myosin heavy chain 10 (MYH10), protein tyrosine phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), Fas apoptotic inhibitory molecule 2 (FAIM2), leucine rich repeats and calponin homology domain containing 1 (LRCH1), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), alpha kinase 3 (ALPK3), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 2 (ENPP2), synaptotagmin like 2 (SYTL2), phospholipase C beta 2 (PLCB2), elastin microfibril interfacier 1 (EMILIN1), cerebellin 3 precursor (CBLN3), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), proline-serine-threonine phosphatase interacting protein 1 (PSTPIP1), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), NLR family pyrin domain containing 12 (NLRP12), chromosome 1 open reading frame 162 (C1orf162), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), oxysterol binding protein like 10 (OSBPL10), atypical chemokine receptor 2 (ACKR2), family with sequence similarity 198 member A (FAM198A / GASK1A), CTD small phosphatase like (CTDSPL), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member L1 (ALDH1L1), ankyrin 2 (ANK2), phosphoinositide-3-kinase regulatory subunit 1 (PIK3R1), ADAM metalloproteinase domain 12 (ADAM12), teneurin transmembrane protein 4 (TENM4), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), serine protease 23 (PRSS23), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), enkurin, TRPC channel interacting protein (ENKUR), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), roundabout guidance receptor 3 (ROBO3), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), myosin IE (MYO1E), SLAM family member 8 (SLAMF8), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), meiosis 1 associated protein (M1AP), trichohyalin (TCHH), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), ELAV like RNA binding protein 4 (ELAVL4), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), HtrA serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), PLAG1 zinc

finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 3124 (C2orf27A / LINC03124), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase 27, atypical (DUSP27), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), NALCN channel auxiliary factor 1 (FAM155A / NALF1), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of PYCR1 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t PYCR1 with PYCR1 – > SEMA3F / CD38 / CD4 / ALOX5 / CD74 / RUNX3 / APBA2 / COL9A2 / COL11A1 / TSPAN32 / GPC4 / ITGB5 / MMP2 / SLC23A2 / SLC22A17 / PCSK5 / DMC1 / NFATC4 / CD40 / RIMS4 / CCL22 / PDGFRL / EPHX3 / PCOLCE / ENG / CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / CRYAB / TSPAN11 / SASH1 / VNN1 / GHR / PARD3B / WLS / IGSF21 / PTCH2 / ENPP2 / C1orf198 / PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / PLAU / BHLHE41 / HCST / TMEM35A / SGCE / PALLD / FCHO1 / LILRB2 / MAP1B /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PYCR1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PYCR1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SEMA3F - PYCR1	256	326	280	212	CD38 - PYCR1	211	356	227	288
CD4 - PYCR1	156	332	299	314	ALOX5 - PYCR1	313	248	303	308
CD74 - PYCR1	360	256	282	390	RUNX3 - PYCR1	312	193	149	241
APBA2 - PYCR1	338	331	258	289	COL9A2 - PYCR1	227	268	144	258
COL11A1 - PYCR1	284	359	127	338	TSPAN32 - PYCR1	225	310	264	301
GPC4 - PYCR1	267	173	204	229	ITGB5 - PYCR1	251	263	340	244
MMP2 - PYCR1	62	199	318	342	SLC23A2 - PYCR1	366	378	236	302
SLC22A17 - PYCR1	282	217	241	224	PCSK5 - PYCR1	253	258	291	286
DMC1 - PYCR1	344	218	117	233	NFATC4 - PYCR1	341	252	195	382
CD40 - PYCR1	139	308	300	379	RIMS4 - PYCR1	238	299	203	353
CCL22 - PYCR1	208	123	246	264	PDGFRL - PYCR1	217	255	219	282
EPHX3 - PYCR1	334	154	209	217	PCOLCE - PYCR1	299	381	196	331
ENG - PYCR1	310	280	198	8	CHRNE - PYCR1	351	279	337	273
CNTNAP1 - PYCR1	359	336	255	361	PMP22 - PYCR1	370	276	247	352
TRIM2 - PYCR1	246	312	192	4	CRYAB - PYCR1	295	270	285	307
TSPAN11 - PYCR1	197	165	244	251	SASH1 - PYCR1	231	313	309	344
VNN1 - PYCR1	377	198	235	2	GHR - PYCR1	207	180	197	266
PARD3B - PYCR1	349	304	229	322	WLS - PYCR1	283	344	336	315
IGSF21 - PYCR1	347	153	308	354	PTCH2 - PYCR1	218	328	297	257
ENPP2 - PYCR1	293	261	272	349	C1orf198 - PYCR1	352	259	269	272
PLXDC2 - PYCR1	356	373	286	300	PDLIM2 - PYCR1	333	303	162	297
CRISPLD1 - PYCR1	138	196	201	362	CCR2 - PYCR1	261	224	283	7
PLAU - PYCR1	273	269	316	350	BHLHE41 - PYCR1	258	233	281	284
HCST - PYCR1	281	354	319	369	TMEM35A - PYCR1	192	366	259	317
SGCE - PYCR1	279	212	194	169	PALLD - PYCR1	249	231	250	190
FCHO1 - PYCR1	368	282	253	380	LILRB2 - PYCR1	265	242	226	378
MAP1B - PYCR1	236	134	206	253	MYH10 - PYCR1	329	317	344	285
PTPN22 - PYCR1	252	327	136	319	FAIM2 - PYCR1	226	57	191	260
LRCH1 - PYCR1	357	311	228	387	LCP1 - PYCR1	84	247	223	324
ALPK3 - PYCR1	372	202	306	293	ENPP2 - PYCR1	293	261	272	349
SYTL2 - PYCR1	229	284	132	214	PLCB2 - PYCR1	160	254	295	383
EMILIN1 - PYCR1	390	285	304	313	CBLN3 - PYCR1	171	306	254	336
FBLN5 - PYCR1	388	320	289	359	PSTPIP1 - PYCR1	158	260	249	247
IGFBP4 - PYCR1	219	287	239	335	NLRP12 - PYCR1	292	239	221	347
C1orf162 - PYCR1	294	220	212	216	RBMS3 - PYCR1	301	245	36	370
OSBPL10 - PYCR1	342	275	180	218	ACKR2 - PYCR1	379	182	294	248
FAM198A - PYCR1	331	215	302	363	CTDSPL - PYCR1	306	214	150	290
ALDH1L1 - PYCR1	365	201	155	228	ANK2 - PYCR1	355	149	213	292
PIK3R1 - PYCR1	203	211	105	206	ADAM12 - PYCR1	194	189	330	283
TENM4 - PYCR1	354	272	215	208	ARID5B - PYCR1	287	329	172	306
PRSS23 - PYCR1	266	155	218	220	CRIM1 - PYCR1	384	262	234	368
ENKUR - PYCR1	319	289	263	351	KCNE4 - PYCR1	264	257	252	356
DDAH1 - PYCR1	369	229	200	318	ROBO3 - PYCR1	157	219	210	278
SUSD3 - PYCR1	257	342	315	321	MYO1E - PYCR1	187	195	288	320
SLAMF8 - PYCR1	325	208	307	279	RUNX1 - PYCR1	340	157	312	332
MIAP - PYCR1	314	290	305	296	TCHH - PYCR1	339	135	311	334
CHCHD6 - PYCR1	234	341	327	375	SIGLEC11 - PYCR1	221	243	179	270
SIGLEC16 - PYCR1	315	264	237	371	LRP5 - PYCR1	345	238	257	298

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between PYCR1 VS Individual members.

MYH10 / PTPN22 / FAIM2 / LRCH1 / LCP1 / ALPK3 / ENPP2 / SYTL2 / PLCB2 /
EMILIN1 / CBLN3 / FBLN5 / PSTPIP1 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 /
OSBPL10 / ACKR2 / FAM198A / CTDSPL / ALDH1L1 / ANK2 / PIK3R1 / ADAM12
/ TENM4 / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 / ENKUR / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS PYCR1									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T PYCR1									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ELAVL4 - PYCR1	327	207	242	231	MXRA8 - PYCR1	248	277	271	312
NLRP3 - PYCR1	262	250	270	325	CCDC74A - PYCR1	74	302	220	294
NKX6-1 - PYCR1	173	216	324	205	APBB2 - PYCR1	240	213	173	268
COL1A2 - PYCR1	291	352	245	309	TMEM71 - PYCR1	232	361	159	326
HTRA1 - PYCR1	228	249	261	364	TVP23A - PYCR1	180	296	287	377
LDHD - PYCR1	328	345	274	3	NT5DC2 - PYCR1	275	205	188	346
FILIP1L - PYCR1	374	315	266	176	RAB31 - PYCR1	308	319	290	343
NPNT - PYCR1	188	228	207	360	ATOH8 - PYCR1	285	360	248	310
VAMP5 - PYCR1	302	253	178	259	CCDC126 - PYCR1	181	294	276	386
GPR183 - PYCR1	320	232	240	291	ITGAM - PYCR1	242	283	225	327
GPR27 - PYCR1	222	221	140	199	MACROD2 - PYCR1	363	241	224	333
IL17D - PYCR1	141	194	260	242	PEAK1 - PYCR1	323	200	317	373
HEG1 - PYCR1	239	79	296	389	P2RY14 - PYCR1	286	73	193	234
YPEL2 - PYCR1	317	293	232	311	FAM131A - PYCR1	271	230	214	340
MAMSTR - PYCR1	161	266	267	276	FZD8 - PYCR1	322	278	251	366
PDE4DIP - PYCR1	296	318	222	358	CSRN3 - PYCR1	335	237	322	384
CIITA - PYCR1	274	170	273	328	KCNE1 - PYCR1	269	295	199	269
PLAG1 - PYCR1	318	226	301	280	EXT1 - PYCR1	289	265	231	385
EPHB3 - PYCR1	276	244	265	355	NEB - PYCR1	117	351	378	250
FAM43B - PYCR1	195	368	366	249	TMEM119 - PYCR1	375	338	384	230
OLFML1 - PYCR1	214	223	370	99	DUSP5P1 - PYCR1	391	323	375	183
ADRA2C - PYCR1	298	377	365	227	PRKD1 - PYCR1	353	390	355	74
CSF1 - PYCR1	91	330	284	299	FLRT2 - PYCR1	326	371	354	200
PRKG1 - PYCR1	135	236	335	330	SHC4 - PYCR1	260	286	385	173
CYP4Z1 - PYCR1	259	297	369	345	CYP4X1 - PYCR1	95	305	373	304
ANKRD20A5P - PYCR1	392	385	390	67	RTN4RL2 - PYCR1	90	267	359	367
C2orf88 - PYCR1	206	337	382	5	KBTBD12 - PYCR1	337	301	343	256
LDLRAD2 - PYCR1	305	347	379	119	ENTPD8 - PYCR1	255	322	364	246
PLAC9 - PYCR1	367	349	352	58	NUGGC - PYCR1	224	355	367	158
FAM180A - PYCR1	358	370	376	130	STK31 - PYCR1	220	291	353	388
MME - PYCR1	371	324	342	66	FAM180B - PYCR1	373	372	380	47
DACT3 - PYCR1	177	357	381	337	ADARB1 - PYCR1	247	369	341	271
SPN - PYCR1	348	292	314	305	C2orf27A - PYCR1	82	340	323	281
DLGAP2 - PYCR1	280	379	372	76	MT1F - PYCR1	250	339	346	255
ITGBL1 - PYCR1	76	353	321	357	MMP17 - PYCR1	324	343	332	83
DLL1 - PYCR1	230	358	328	195	ZNF521 - PYCR1	381	365	357	28
RYR3 - PYCR1	304	384	389	53	DUSP27 - PYCR1	40	273	331	295
RNU6-529P - PYCR1	223	348	368	391	RHOT1P2 - PYCR1	382	389	313	112
PLPP4 - PYCR1	386	375	388	136	SYT15 - PYCR1	241	325	387	210
FAM155A - PYCR1	383	387	377	117	VIT - PYCR1	385	388	298	68
ANKRD20A9P - PYCR1	389	391	360	60	GPX3 - PYCR1	378	386	361	36
HMGB3P7 - PYCR1	376	314	371	128	ANKRD20A11P - PYCR1	380	383	391	31
TENM3 - PYCR1	300	393	351	57	RFPL1S - PYCR1	184	363	348	392
LINC00937 - PYCR1	263	335	349	372	LINC01907 - PYCR1	186	281	383	381
ITGB2-AS1 - PYCR1	270	374	334	187	LMCD1-AS1 - PYCR1	343	321	358	160
CYP4F29P - PYCR1	303	382	339	116	ZNF883 - PYCR1	201	346	320	341
SNX18P13 - PYCR1	387	334	350	95					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between PYCR1 VS Individual members.

SUSD3 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / CCDC74A / NKX6-1 / APBB2 / COL1A2 / TMEM71 / HTRA1 / TVP23A / LDHD / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / CCDC126 / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MACROD2 / IL17D / PEAK1 / HEG1 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / MAMSTR / FZD8 / PDE4DIP / CSRN3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / EPHB3 / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1

/ SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / MME / FAM180B / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP29 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / VIT / ANKRD20A9P / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t PYCR1

SEMA3F / CD38 / CD4 / ALOX5 / CD74 / RUNX3 / APBA2 ...
 COL9A2 / COL11A1 / TSPAN32 / GPC4 / ITGB5 / MMP2 ...
 SLC23A2 / SLC22A17 / PCSK5 / DMC1 / NFATC4 / CD40 ...
 RIMS4 / CCL22 / PDGFRL / EPHX3 / PCOLCE / ENG ...
 CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / CRYAB / TSPAN11 ...
 SASH1 / VNN1 / GHR / PARD3B / WLS / IGSF21 / PTCH2 ...
 ENPP2 / C1orf198 / PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 ...
 PLAU / BHLHE41 / HCST / TMEM35A / SGCE / PALLD / FCHO1 ...
 LILRB2 / MAP1B / MYH10 / PTPN22 / FAIM2 / LRCH1 / LCP1 ...
 ALPK3 / ENPP2 / SYTL2 / PLCB2 / EMILIN1 / CBLN3 ...
 FBLN5 / PSTPIP1 / IGFBP4 / NLRP12 / C1orf162 / RBMS3 ...
 OSBPL10 / ACKR2 / FAM198A / CTDSPL / ALDH1L1 / ANK2 ...
 PIK3R1 / ADAM12 / TENM4 / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 ...
 ENKUR / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 / SUSD3 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 ...
 RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 ...
 LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / CCDC74A / NKX6-1 ...
 APBB2 / COL1A2 / TMEM71 / HTRA1 / TVP23A / LDHD ...
 NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 ...
 CCDC126 / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MACROD2 / IL17D ...
 PEAK1 / HEG1 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / MAMSTR ...
 FZD8 / PDE4DIP / CSRN3P3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / PLAG1 ...
 EXT1 / EPHB3 / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 ...
 DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 ...
 SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P / RTN4RL2 ...
 C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 ...
 NUGGC / FAM180A / STK31 / MME / FAM180B / DACT3 ...
 ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 ...
 MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 / RYR3 / DUSP29 / RNU6-529P ...
 RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / VIT / ANKRD20A9P ...
 GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / RFPL1S ...
 LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 ...
 CYP4F29P / ZNF883 / SNX18P13

PYCR1

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between PYCR1 and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic PYCR1 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of PYCR1-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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